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**PERFORMANCE OF BORASSUS WOOD IN A CONCESSION IN FRONT OF
WATER AND FIRE****LOLO Komlan^{*1}, BANAKINAO Sinko², AFIO Ayarema³**^{1,2,3}Laboratory of Structure and Mechanics of Materials (LaS2M), University of Lome^{1,3}Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Lome, 01 BP 1515 Lome 01 – TOGO²Department of Civil Engineering, University of Lome, 01 BP 1515 Lome 01 – TOGO.

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ABSTRACT

Borassus is a very resistant timber in West Africa but little known. The remains of its tin constructions testify to this property. These constructions are likely to suffer damage such as fire, degradation due to moisture, aging. The presence of these damages weakens the performance of the wood used in construction. The objective of this work is to make this timber visible through its mechanical performance and resistance to fire, water and aging.

An excavation study of the old concessions is coupled with the experimental one. Fire resistance is made on ten samples taken from the middle zone or the core of the stipe, ten on the periphery (hard zone) of the stipe and ten others between the middle and the periphery of each case considered. The influence of moisture is tested by rainwater and sea water absorption. To evaluate the performance of the Borassus in case of fire, a simulation of about thirty samples (ten per category) is made on a gas stove. The rate of ash produced is the result of the carbonization of borassus. The water absorption examination is done for thirty-six (36) days. The samples behave identically. Each category exhibits the same behavior after twenty (20) days. The samples were quickly absorbed within ten (10) days, regardless of the type of water. Faced with the stove fire, the behaviors differed slightly but similar to each other. Binders have disappeared to the detriment of fibers.

As part of this study, the behavior of Borassus wood against moisture and/or fire highlights the quality of the durable hold of Borassus. Borassus maintains its good performance against water and fire in the hard zone.

1. INTRODUCTION

Man lives under the shelter of constructions made of various materials including wood, metal and straw. Wood, an ancient and natural material, is used in several fields : construction, furniture and energy. A material with several advantages, wood has some weaknesses due to its natural origin. In construction, the frames are made of solid wood. Concessions are, in nature, subject to bad weather due to temperature heating, the presence of humidity or the nature of the material. The result of the persistence of these phenomena produces disastrous effects, not all of which are predictable.

The heating of the temperature favors the development of fire that can become catastrophic. The action leads to real difficulties (fire). A fire can lead to death and leave sequelae in the life of the victim. It can cause a lot of material damage such as the loss of property, the collapse of a concession, negative impacts on the population beyond the capacity of the community to react. The fire resistance of wooden structures remains and remains a sensitive subject. In concessions, the sources of fire are diverse : an electrical short circuit, a lamp post placed too close to a curtain, a fir tree garland, non-compliant electrical installations, a cigarette, a candle, cooking oil, a match or a lighter [1]. The reaction of the concession differs from the materials used for fire or fire propagation. During the fire, a reaction occurs in which the wood disappears in favor of ash formation. However, wood is classified according to the NF standard. P. 92.507, standard established by the Scientific and Technical Centre for Building (CSTB) among non-flammable fuels (M1) and moderately flammable fuels (M4) [2].

Work was done on wood, wood combustion, fire and fire spread. During a fire, materials undergo temperature-dependent transformations. The behavior of the wood exposed to fire, the flame spread index characterizes the resistance capacity of the wood. In a fire situation, the surface temperature rises very quickly to its ignition point between 250 and 300°C [3]. However, the main compounds in wood in general are cellulose, lignin and hemicelluloses [4] which are composed of carbon cells. In front of the fire, some compounds are volatile. During combustion, the temperature of the fire is very variable between 1800 and 3000 °C on the other hand in case of a fire, it varies between 200 °C to 600 °C depending on the species of wood, its water content and its density [3]. The destruction of materials like wood and steel is mostly caused by moisture. Humidity is therefore a factor of slow destruction. It produces mold, rots reducing the strength of the material. Conservatory places are not spared. Thus, a relative humidity of 50±3% is an acceptable variant [5].

Borassus is an anhydride wood, it has no bound water. It is composed of intertwined and intertwined fibers [6]. Fibers are carbonaceous compounds. Borassus is a palm-like wood considered a false wood [7]. The stem, the false trunk, is composed of fibers of varying intensity depending on the area considered on the radius of the trunk. The stem, the false trunk, is composed of fibers of varying intensity depending on the area considered on the radius of the trunk. The fibers are therefore long hard sheaths of black colors detachable from each other. The fibers intertwined in a whitish body. They are black and are surrounded by a substance that holds them together: it is the glue or binder. Binders coat the fibers and provide the rigid bond between the fibers. In the constitution of Borassus celluloses are the fibers representing the largest part of the trunk or about 60%, come lignins or 19%, hemicelluloses or 10% and extracts or 7% [8]. The bound water is crippled in the stem. There are two borassus subjects: male and female [7]. The male subject does not bear fruit, but the female subject bears fruit. The plant can reach 15 to 18 m whose stem diameter varies according to the environment and can measure 30 to 80 cm in diameter. The age of the plant can reach 120 years. From the mechanical point of view, the male is more resistant. For most cases, the male subject is more used in construction.

An investigation is carried out on the constructions made with the Borassus. It remains our motivation and is a basic witness for this study. Borassus is resistant to termites, xylophagous and moisture. The more the borassus slice is exposed to the open air, the more mechanically resistant it becomes [9] [10]. Unfortunately, Borassus wood was abandoned in favor of other woods such as iroko, mahogany, teak [9] and industrial woods. Constructions of the latter have not had their time. Iroko, mahogany and teak woods are eaten away by termites, xylophagous and even mechanically reduced by water. Concessions from the colonial period (fig.1.a), such the slave house in/at Agbodrafo, Togo (fig. 1.b), remain vestiges to this day. From the bark to the center (marrow) of the trunk, the hardness decreases, the density of the fibers also decreases. But in constructions, the bark part is used (fig.1.c).

Figure 1 : Borassus wooden constructions

No studies are done on the damage to this wood. It is recognized as very durable, resistant to xylophages and rot-proof. None has proven that it becomes harder in its aging. In this article, the objective is to enhance the quality of borassus to resist degradation due to moisture, fire resistance and to show the spectacular aging of borassus. To do this, the behavior of the roof made of Borassus is examined from top to bottom by the old illustrations and showing the behavior of the borassus exposed to fire and to determine the speed of propagation and its hygroscopic behavior.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study materials are borassus wood (fig.2.a), the 6.5 kg gas cylinder and a fire activation source (match logs or lighters) which are tested in the open air after a test is carried out in the kiln. Salt water (seawater) and rainwater (freshwater) basins will be used to test the water absorption and strength of Borassus wood.

The stem of borassus is divided into slices and is used as timber for concessions in West Africa and more particularly in Togo (fig. 1). The slices of this wood are used as beams or breaks in a frame. Borassus wood is a male tree about 25 years old with a height of 15 meters and a diameter in the center of 0.85 meters. All the potential for resistance of the stipe is acquired with the increase in age. By transversely cutting the stem, three zones were created for our study of the bark in the center of the stem: zone A (hard part or duramen), zone B (sapwood) and zone C (spongy part or heart). Figure 2.a shows the Borassus wood seedling. Figure 2.b shows the emptied stipe of the spongy part. This rest is exploited in construction. The trunk of the plant is divided into slices in the form of a breakdown. But we will take them to much smaller dimensions. Specimens of 20 x 20 x 240 mm are taken from this wood. The moisture content of these test pieces used is about 14% at 105 °C.

Figure 2 : The tree and the different treatments

This type of wood is used in construction. The risk of collapse related to the fire remains relevant during an excessive heating of heat creating a disaster: the fire. The sources of fire are multiple producing a flame difficult to control. The flame spreads and reaches the roof. The shape of the roofs is broken and the frame is made of ronier. Here, the roofs presented are made of sheet metal (fig. 2). Whether covered with sheet metal or straw, fire occurs when conditions are met.

The experiment is carried out on in test tubes comparable to crossbowmen, punches or an entrance on a frame. The test tubes are placed in the furnace. The samples of the spongy part are first put in the oven for about three (3) minutes. A significant production of smoke is observed, then the specimens of zone B, then zone A. For the same duration, the smoke observed is less important for the test pieces of zone B. The same observation is made for zone A. So the oven technique is not appropriate. The specimens are quickly removed due to smoke production.

a. Gas cylinderb. or c. Simulation of exposed borassus samples from fire**Figure 3 : Exhibition of test equipment**

The experiment is repeated with other specimens on a gas cylinder (fig.3). After turning the valve counterclockwise, the gas cylinder allows the butane gas to pass through. From a match stick as an activation energy source, the flame is produced. The test tubes are exposed to fire from a stove burner. A gas burner, the classic one, is used. The gas cylinder remains the source of continuous flame supply or activation. The flame produced is adjusted and maintained so as to have the bright blue color. The temperature of the fire flame does not reach that of the stove. There was no thermometer to measure the temperature of combustion. The duration of the experience is five (5) minutes. The permanent heat source is produced by the flame from the butane gas cylinder to determine the burning rate of the firewood in the fire. The gas cylinder used is a cylinder of 6.5 kg mass. It is usually used for cooking. This is the liquefied petroleum gas called LPG. This gas changes from liquid to gaseous when the valve is opened. The gas boils during evaporation and produces cold. . The flame of the burner has a blue color. But burning wood gives a red/orange color.

Pieces of wood with dimensions $20 \times 20 \times 180 \text{ mm}^3$ are subjected to a temperature above $1500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ where the flame is yellow for 3 min and 5 min. During these times, the reaction of the wood is observed at the fraction of seconds. No sensors or detectors are used to measure temperature or analyze the fumes released. Ash is produced by removal of organic matter from the material sample by calcination at a defined temperature over a given time. In our case, the initial mass is recorded before the experiment and after exposure, a new mass is recorded again.

Moisture degrades the mechanical strength of wood. To show the resistance of borassus in the presence of moisture, pieces of borassus are put in water about twenty-five (25) days. The pieces are taken in the hard part of the stipe, part used in construction. Seawater and distilled water are considered. Sea water is salty but distilled water is fresh. The goal is to see if the salty components will react by breaking the molecular chains of borassus.

Figure 4 : Immersion Testing

Three types of samples are tested : Machined sample (U), Bark sample (E) and Spongy area sample (S). To find out the saturation time and the volume of water absorbed, ten (10) samples in distilled and salt water. The dimensions of these test pieces are 15 x 20 x 30 mm³ having a mass (M) in g before immersion. Weight measurements are taken during the experiment. The samples were polished at the Struers brand polishing machine with 220-inch sandpaper, the water is used to remove the chips.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The room contains mostly combustible objects including furniture sometimes made of wood. The materials used for furniture are made in tropical Africa of several types of wood less resistant than the ronier of the scientific name borassus used in construction for a long time. Wood products resist burning and maintain structural integrity while continuing to provide protection when exposed to fire or heat because of its ability to resist ignition and produce a low rate of heat release.

The variation in the amount of material consumed is proportional to the constituents. The law of this reaction will be similar to an equation of the chemical reaction translated as follows (eq. 1) :

where A and B are constituents of the reaction,
 α and β are the coefficients of participation in the reaction,
 γ and δ are the shares of the derivatives of the reaction,
 C and D are the derivatives of the reaction.

In our case here, borassus and oxygen are the constituents of the reaction and smoke, ash and the rest of the burnt wood are the derivatives. The proportion of participation of each of the constituents in the development of fire varies. The constituents of the reaction disappear in favor of others that are formed. This reaction will not be fully used in this illustration.

The phenomenon follows the law of rate of evolution of a chemical system related to temperature, the concentration of components. The rates of disappearance and formation are proportional to the production of smoke and ash according to the relationship (eq. 2) :

$$1/\alpha \vartheta_{dA}=1/\beta \vartheta_{dB}= 1/\gamma \vartheta_{dC}=1/\delta \vartheta_{dD} \quad (2)$$

where the rate ϑ_{di} are the volumetric velocities related to or proportional to the concentration coefficients of the constituents present.

Experimental measurements have shown that the rate of disappearance is proportional to the rate of carbonization. Several bodies resulted from the reaction. Ash is produced at a certain rate of charring or fire spread. The burning rate, ash production depends on the species of wood. The study of the ash rate is made on the ronier after exposing the wood to a temperature of 300 ° C for 3 min in the oven. A large amount of smoke

has occurred when the test tubes of the heart are introduced. Smoke generation for Zone B has decreased slightly. The same applies to the bark area. The fumes are produced thanks to the binders or matrix in which the fibers dough. The stem of borassus is not intended to make fire. Depending on the area of exploitation of the stem of the bark in the center, the classification makes it possible to take into account the release of smoke. So borassus is of class s3, a steaming wood.

The study is resumed around the stove, around the gas cylinder. The ash content highlights the existence of fibers. The production of ash levels results from the mineral elements drawn from the soil by the plant. The ash content corresponds to the ratio of the mass of residues obtained after calcination to the initial mass of the sample, expressed as a percentage (eq. 3) :

$$t_c\% = \frac{M_c}{M_i} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Where $t_c\%$: ash rate, M_c : charred mass, M_i : initial mass or mass before carbonization.

Table 1 : Determination of ash content

Part of the wood	Mass before carbonization M_i (g)	Mass after carbonization M (g)	Charred mass M_c (g)	Ash rate $\frac{M_c}{M_i} \times 100$	Average
Spongy part or heart	20,38	15,04	5,34	26,2	25,31
	20,59	15,65	4,94	23,99	
	23,5	17,45	6,05	25,74	
Sapwood	35,5	23,75	11,75	33,1	31,51
	35,3	24,01	11,29	31,98	
	31,38	22,14	9,24	29,45	
Hard part or Heartwood	41,76	27,61	14,15	33,88	33,19
	39,27	26,01	13,26	33,77	
	48,29	32,87	15,42	31,93	

The rate of ash produced is lower in the heart of this wood than in the bark. At the heart of borassus, binders are dominant and are responsible for the smoke. At the periphery of the stipe (duramen), the fibers are also dominant and are responsible for the production of ash. Flammability increases as the density and moisture of the wood decreases. Figure 5 shows the result after the furnace test. The binders are charred at the core; In sapwood, the presence of binders with the fibers activated combustion. In the duramen, the few binders quickly disappeared in front of the fire.

Figure 5 : Results of the pieces tested (charred areas)

Borassus does not have pores as in ordinary wood. The fibers do not carry pores. They do not keep water bound. Alveoli are observable in binders [8] [11]. Figure 4 is the result of the samples placed in water. The curves with ordinates around 0.5 are the results of the hard zone samples (machined designated U and Ecorce designated E). The heart is spongy so designated by S. This area absorbs a lot of water. Borassus is a wood that has no pores or holes in the fibers. The binders between the black fibers reserve the immersion of water. Overall, Borassus absorbs within the first five (5) days and then stabilizes. Figures 6.a and b show the macroscopic structures of borassus.

Microscopic observation showing the fibers in black and the alveoli
 Tomography observation showing black fibers and alveoli

Immersion curves of borassus samples

Immersion curves of borassus samples

Figure 6 : Characterization in proportion of water saturation of borassus

Water absorption in both (02) cases is similar. The type of water has no influence on the test. Only the sampling area has an impact on the study. The bark or machined parts, being hard, have difficulty absorbing water. Figure 6.c is the characterization of the water saturation of borassus.

CONCLUSION

Physical mechanical investigations on borassus show the qualities of this wood. The concessions made in borassus remain intact, stable and solid lengthening the time of collapse of the building. The ability to spread fire is slow because of the presence of fibers. The absence of a thermometer prevented the gradual reveal of transformation phases during reactions. The rot-proofing of borassus is shown by immersion curves showing low water absorption in the hard zone of borassus.

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